

Documentation on the Model toolbox with guidelines and training tutorials for supporting the national model runs

EJP SOIL - CarboSeq
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CarboSeq handout

Introduction

The modelToolBox inherits from the development of a previous software aiming at simulating the soil organic carbon (SOC) changes using various models and on diverse datasets, carried out during the French ADEME Csopra project. These developments were continued during the course of the EJP-SOIL CarboSeq project, with specific simulation protocols developed for fulfilling the project objectives.

The modelToolBox aims to provide a tool that supports both advanced and basic use for users interested in SOC dynamics modelling, addressing both researchers who require specific model configurations and users who are unfamiliar with the subject. Typically, this latter usage is the test case considered for CarboSeq national runs.

Another aspect behind the modelToolBox and its several components is to provide an enhanced level of interoperability between data sources required for biogeochemical modelling and the models themselves. The modelToolBox has been and will continue to be used for data streams beyond those considered in the CarboSeq project, therefore the import of data into the model toolbox will require mechanisms based on ontologies and semantic web mechanisms.

The modelToolBox offers several parameterization options for simulating SOC dynamics models. For CarboSeq users, we have restricted ourselves to the most basic options. In the following we will present only the modelToolBox for the CarboSeq project and explain how to use it for CarboSeq simulations.

Description of the modelToolBox

Components used by the modelToolBox to run the simulations.

First, the input files are first passed through a service which checks their semantics. This check will, among others, evaluate if the column names are well formed and if the character strings used in the non-numeric columns actually use codes that are known by the modelToolBox. These codes are defined in a specific ontology

The basic structure of the modelToolBox

Figure 1: The basic structure of the modelToolBox

developed especially for the modelToolBox.

Then, the modelToolBox retrieves climate data from an online climate service and calculates carbon inputs using published allometric functions. The following sections provide more detailed information on these two components.

The amount of mineralized carbon is estimated from management, soil and climate data, and the amount of carbon input is estimated from management data.

Finally, the modelToolBox will run the RothC model through the `soilr` R package. Three versions of RothC will be run: the standard version for any plant material, an adapted version for organic fertilization excluding biochars, and a third adapted version for biochars. These modified versions are provided by partners of WP3 in the CarboSeq project.

Carbon input estimation function

The modelToolBox estimates the carbon inputs attached to the main crops from yield data, using a module called `cinest`, which was proposed by the Thünen Institute. Several allometric functions are available, but the CarboSeq protocol uses by default the Bolinder allometric functions.

The climate service

The climatic data is retrieved from longitude/latitude attached to each simulation site. The European scale climate data used for this exercise are the AgERA5 data set and associated AgERA5_ET0 where PET is computed based on the FAO 56 Penman-Monteith method (as described in FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper 56). A more complete description of the dataset is given in Parisse et al. (2023)¹.

here : <https://nextcloud.inrae.fr/f/133943870>.

How carbon farming measures are modeled

Soil tillage

Soil tillage is not implemented in the CarboSeq modeltoolbox as RothC was not so far parameterized for that measure.

¹Parisse Barbara, Alilla Roberta, & De Natale Flora. (2023). EJPSOIL CarboSeq agrometeorological datasets (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399180>

Residue management

This is represented by the *prop_residue_removal* parameter of crop.csv input files, and used then as an input for the *cinest* function, which estimates carbon input into the soils from yield data of the main crops.

Temporary grasslands (or leys)

This measure is not implemented yet.

Organic amendments

Type and quantities of organic amendments can be specified through the crop.csv file. This is in turn used to specify amounts of C flowing into the compartments of RothC, and is based on parameterization proposed by the WP3 of the CarboSeq project.

Note that Biochar amendments are a specific case where a specific version of the RothC model, with specific SOC compartments, comes into play. This new version was also proposed by the WP3.

Agroforestry

Assuming users are able to estimate the additional C input into the soil from agroforestry, this will taken into account in the simulations. Any quantities declared in the *C_WOODY_ELEMENTS* column will be considered as C input into the soils with a C DPM:RPM ratio of 0.25.

Cover crops

Cover crops can be declared in the crop.csv file in the *CI_CC* column (see below). Then a standard carbon input of 3.32 Mg/C/year will be applied. This value was deduced as the mean value for temperate regions from a literature review (Martin et al. in prep). It is likely to overestimate the carbon inputs under arid climates. Improvements of this measure are planned in the near future.

Practical use of the modelToolBox

Where to find it

CarboSeq users will access to the modelToolBox through an online tool, which we refer to as the *csopra_lab*. Although other ways of using the modelToolBox are possible, such as installing the modelToolBox R packages remotely, online usage was preferred. This ensures that everyone shares the same configuration and facilitates problem-solving if any arise.

The address of the lab is: <https://coby.infosol.inrae.fr:8080/>. Note that a *development* version of the lab is also made available at <https://147.100.203.110/>.

HowToLab

Figure 2: HowToLab

There we test latest changes to the modeltoolbox and there you will get the latest bug fixes, at the price of less stable system.

The users need to create an account in order to access the lab. If then the access is not automatically granted, please email <mailto:julien.wengler@inrae.fr> to be manually authorized.

When signed in, select the “csopra_lab” image and start the server.

Once connected, you will see on the left of the screen the folder panel. By default, you are in [user root]/shared, which is a read-only folder designed only to provide a default dataset (the inputFiles folder) and a python notebook (see blue arrow) which contains the basic commands to execute.

To upload your own datasets, please go up to your user root (see red arrow) and create (sub)folders. Each folder can only contain one set of crop+soil+units csv, and these files cannot be renamed. If you want to test several datasets, please use separate folders.

To run the modeltoolbox, follow the python notebook, replacing ~/shared/inputFiles/ by the data folder you wish to use.

Here is a graphical example :

The input csv files

Creating the input csv files, i.e. your dataset, is probably the biggest part of the work you have to do. They are composed of three files: `crop.csv` (information about the crop rotations and agricultural practices), `soil.csv` (information on the soil properties and the sites locations), `units.csv` (units used in the other files). These file names **must not be changed**.

Climate will be inferred by the modelToolBox from latitude/longitude coordinates of the simulation points, as described above (see below the section about climate data). The simulation grid, whether at a national or European scale, will consist of a 10km x 10km resolution grid. This means the crop and soil data entered must be representative of the 100 km² square unit represented by every simulation point on the grid.

Please note that the files `crop.csv` and `soil.csv` must contain the same number of sites, or IDs².

General formatting comments: - column separators should be the comma : ‘,’ - missing values are allowed in some columns (see bellow) but in any case

²But not the same number of rows, because one location is one row in `soil.csv`, but as many rows as years in the simulation in `crop.csv`.

should be, if allowed, indicated by an empty value (i.e. ,“”, or ,,).

Crop data : the crop.csv file

Each simulation point has a unique ID identifier. Crop data is requested for each point, including crop rotation, including monoculture, which is representative of current cropland management. Within the framework of CarboSeq, this rotation should be looped in order to produce a sequence of exactly 20 years (truncate the last iteration if necessary). The input file will be made of a number of rows equal to (n simulation points \times 20). For each simulation point, it is assumed that there is one main crop per year. Therefore, each of the 20 rotation rows corresponds to one main crop from the crop rotation.

Each row will be informed by the following variables (column names), and *the input file should not include any missing value*, except when stated otherwise. The order of the columns does not matter. Optional columns are indicated by the flag “**optional**”.

- *ID* : id of the simulation point
- *NUM* : position in the 20 years rotation sequence
- *SOWING_DATE* : sowing date in format %d-%m (for instance 01-02) or %Y-%d-%m if you need/want to force a specific year
- *HARVEST_DATE* : harvest date in format %d-%m (for instance 01-09) or %Y-%d-%m if you need/want to force a specific year
- *CROP* : crop name, taken from a specific thesaurus (see below)
- If you know exactly how much carbon is deposited by the main crop, fill these two fields.
 - **C_plant_AG** (**optional**): amount of carbon entering the soil from above-ground plant during the growing season and after harvest (including crop residues left on the field) [unit tC/ha]
 - **C_plant_BG** (**optional**): amount of carbon entering the soil from below-ground plant during the growing season and after harvest [unit tC/ha]
- Otherwise, leave those above columns blank. The C input will be computed on the basis of the following fields (ignored if at least one of *C_plant_AG* and *C_plant_BG* is specified):
 - *Yield* : dry matter yield of the main crop, e.g. grain weight for cereal, fruit weight for fruit trees, etc.. [unit t/ha]
 - *prop_residue_removal* : fraction of crop aboveground residues removed from the field [between 0 and 1]

– *Cin_method* (**optional**): the allometric approach used for that specific crop when computing Cinputs based on yield. Can take values in [bolinder, ipcc, weiser, franko, ctool]. See Dechow et al. (2019) for reference. For Carboseq, the default method (unless you specifies values in this column) will be “ipcc”. If this optional column is given as input, and in it some NAs are found, we also fall back for these NAs to the default method. That is, you may specify specific allometric function only for some specific crops.

- *EOM_C* : carbon inputs related to organic fertilization) [unit tC/ha/yr],
- *EOM_TYPE* : name of the product used for organic fertilisation (taken from a specific thesaurus, see below). If EOM_C=0, the type is ignored, but you still have to enter something that fits the thesaurus.
- *CI_CC* : logical value: 0 if no cover crop, 1 if there is a cover crop
- *Irrig* : irrigation amount [unit mm]
- *BIOCHAR_C* : carbon inputs related to Biochar amendments) [unit tC/ha/yr]
- *C_WOODY_ELEMENTS* : extra carbon input attached to Agroforestry with hedges-hedgerows planting, [unit tC/ha/yr],

Semantic check: the thesaurus

In order for `crop.csv` to work properly, CROP and EOM_TYPE fields must have values that match a particular thesaurus: they must be included in the csopra ontology. Therefore, it is crucial for partners to verify that the words they use in their input files are included in the list of concepts understood by the software.

The list of this concepts is available at <https://csopra.pages.mia.inra.fr/OWLifier/concepts.html>.

The word spelling test is NOT case sensitive.

Site and soil data : the soil.csv file

As for the crop input data, the soil data relates to the simulation points on the 10km×10km simulation grid, each simulation point being identified by a unique ID identifier. In contrast, the `soil.csv` input file should have only one row per simulation point.

- *ID* : id of the simulation point
- *START_YEAR* : beginning of the simulation, equal to 2000
- *LON* : longitude [unit ° in decimal]
- *LAT* : latitude [unit ° in decimal]

- *CLAY* : clay content [unit %]
- *OC_THA* : 0-30cm soil organic carbon stock, estimated by taking into account OC content, bulk density and the percentage (ideally the mass percentage) of coarse fragments [unit tC/ha].

The two variables below *must be present* in the `soil.csv` files, but since they are not used in the CarboSeq simulations for now, those columns *might include missing data*. They were kept in order to allow the simulation of other models such as the AMG model.

- *SILT* : silt content [unit %],
- *pH* : soil pH

Two optional columns serve to qualify the initial distribution of SOC in RothC pools:

- *C_QUALITY* : proportions of C in the 5 RothC pools, separated by slashes and enclosed by parentheses. For instance : “(0.1/0.1/0/0.6/0.2)”. This is used only if the RothC runner actually runs the simulations, and not another model. If this column is present, it will supersede the standard initialization procedure where the C is distributed among pools according to the C inputs during the simulation, assuming that past management is similar to future management.
- *C_QUALITY_TYPE* : for the CarboSeq exercise, this should be exactly : “(DPM/RPM/BIO/HUM/IOM)”. This is mandatory for the *C_QUALITY* column to be used).

Units : the `units.csv` file

Each row in this file specifies the unit in which is expressed a quantity in the previous files. These units supersede the units indicated above, that is to say that the values in the previous csv files must correspond to the units actually written in `units.csv`. The modeltoolbox will take care of the potential conversions.

Running the simulations

First of all, we load the modeltoolbox library.

```
library(modeltoolbox)
```

The first command, `loadCSVs`, will load the `.csv` input files located in the `inputFiles` directory. A second command, `runSims` will run the simulations and a third one, `readSocForcingsResults` will enable to retrieve the results, with can be exported, used for drawing plots, etc.

Loading the csv files

We load the csv files via the `loadCSVs` command, with a first argument indicating the path to the folder containing the `crop.csv` and `soil.csv` files. If no path is provided, the default template (`inputFiles` folder) is used.

```
# Load all the data from the default template  
loadCSVs()
```

Optional arguments include: `* ids` = a vector containing the IDs that you want to selectively load.

Loading the CSV files include a semantic check, the renaming of the elements according to the ontology, and the creation of 8 other files which are the actual input files of the program.

Running the simulation

We run the simulation simply with the command `runSims`

```
# run the simulation for all ids (default)  
runSims()
```

Like for `loadCSVs`, you can selectively compute some IDs:

```
# Example: run the simulation for the id 2  
runSims(usmIds=list(2))
```

Looking at the results

```
res <- readSocForcingsResults(maxCores = 1)
```

This command will retrieve the results of the simulation and store them in the list `res`. This comprises two dataframes: `SOC` and `forcings`, detailed below.

You may want to refer to the documentation of the `readSocForcingsResults` function (type `?readSocForcingsResults`) for a full detail of the outputs, for the RothC model.

SOC

The `SOC` dataframe is simply the SOC values for each simulated month and each simulation unit. SOC changes may be plotted with the standard R tools as defined below.

```
# display the first 5 rows of the simulated SOC  
head(res$SOC, 5)  
#>   ID ID_SUCC   DATE   SOC  
#> 1  1      1 2000-01-01 167.78  
#> 2  1      1 2000-02-01 168.36  
#> 3  1      1 2000-03-01 167.76
```

plot of chunk unnamed-chunk-6

Figure 3: plot of chunk unnamed-chunk-6

```
#> 4 1 1 2000-04-01 167.14
#> 5 1 1 2000-05-01 166.77
# plot the SOC evolution with time for all the IDs
lattice::xyplot(SOC~DATE, groups = ID,
               res$SOC, type = "l",
               ylab = "SOC (tC/ha)")
```

From the `csopra_lab`, this object can be saved to the user space as shown below, and then downloaded from the `csopra_lab` on your personal computer for further analysis (on the left panel, select the file, right-click, download).

```
## Saving the data
write.csv(res$SOC, file = "~/simResult.csv")
```

Forcings

The `forcings` dataframe contains the data given as an input to RochC. Each line corresponds to one month for one specific unit of simulation (ID)

The columns “CInputsAGCrop”, “CInputsBGCrop” and “CInputs” represent the carbon input from the culture residues, respectively above ground, below ground and total (sum of both).

```
head(res$forcings[, c("ID", "DATE", "CInputsAGCrop", "CInputsBGCrop", "CInputs") ], 5)
#>  ID      DATE CInputsAGCrop CInputsBGCrop  CInputs
#> 1  1 2000-01-01 0.0000000 0.00000000 0.00000000
#> 2  1 2000-02-01 0.0006811 0.00024235 0.00092345
#> 3  1 2000-03-01 0.0022882 0.00081421 0.00310242
#> 4  1 2000-04-01 0.0037494 0.00133413 0.00508351
#> 5  1 2000-05-01 0.0054605 0.00194300 0.00740350
```

The following columns represent the external carbon inputs. “EOM” is the amount of organic fertilization, whose DPM/RPM/HUM ratio is given by the “DPM”, “RPM” and “HUM” columns. “CWoodyElements” is the amount of carbon input through woody features (hedgerows...). “BC” is the amount of biochar brought to the soil.

```
head(res$forcings[, c("ID", "DATE", "EOM", "DPM", "RPM", "HUM", "CWoodyElements", "BC")],
#>  ID      DATE EOM  DPM  RPM HUM CWoodyElements BC
#> 1  1 2000-01-01 1.13 0.0452 1.0848 0 0 0.1
#> 2  1 2000-02-01 0.00 0.0000 0.0000 0 0 0.0
#> 3  1 2000-03-01 0.00 0.0000 0.0000 0 0 0.0
#> 4  1 2000-04-01 0.00 0.0000 0.0000 0 0 0.0
#> 5  1 2000-05-01 0.00 0.0000 0.0000 0 0 0.0
```

The following columns refer to climatic aspects. “covered” indicates if the soil is covered by a crop. “temp” and “rain” refer to temperature and rainfall, while “pet” refers to evapotranspiration.

```
head(res$forcings[, c("ID", "DATE", "covered", "temp", "rain", "pet")], 5)
#>   ID      DATE covered temp rain  pet
#> 1  1 2000-01-01      0  5.70 55.01 27.55
#> 2  1 2000-02-01      1  6.35 55.76 38.17
#> 3  1 2000-03-01      1  9.00 59.13 65.26
#> 4  1 2000-04-01      1 11.70 62.51 85.68
#> 5  1 2000-05-01      1 16.08 54.78 124.47
```

Finally, the “As”, “Bs” and “Cs” relate to the mineralization factors, while “rhos” is the aggregated mineralization modifier for RothC.

```
head(res$forcings[, c("ID", "DATE", "As", "Cs", "Bs", "rhos")], 5)
#>   ID      DATE      As Cs      Bs  rhos
#> 1  1 2000-01-01 0.56707 1.0 1.00000 0.56707
#> 2  1 2000-02-01 0.63640 0.6 1.00000 0.38184
#> 3  1 2000-03-01 0.96061 0.6 1.00000 0.57637
#> 4  1 2000-04-01 1.35232 0.6 0.64136 0.52039
#> 5  1 2000-05-01 2.08986 0.6 0.20000 0.25078
```

Troubleshooting

More information about the runs

The easiest and most straightforward thing to do if you face some difficulties is to ask the modeltoolbox to display more information about the runs. Most of the time, some warning or error messages are generated (but by default, not displayed), before the execution stops and before you get some obscure error messages. Asking for more information, also called logs, can be done like this :

```
csopratools::switch_to_jupyter_appender()
```

Optionnaly, while asking for support (see below), you can send us a copy for these logs, which might help us to understand what is going on.

Once you are done with debugging, you can return to the normal logging mode, which more silent, by doing :

```
csopratools::switch_to_console_appender()
```

Error feedback

We invite users to report any issue they encounter in the use of the modeltoolbox.

Early users (beta-testers) of the modeltoolbox are particularly encouraged to test as many different situations as possible to track software bugs.

To share issues and their solutions with the developers and among the users, you are welcome to join this Mattermost instance.

References

Dechow, R., Franko, U., Kätterer, T., Kolbe, H., 2019. Evaluation of the RothC model as a prognostic tool for the prediction of SOC trends in response to management practices on arable land. *Geoderma* 337, 463–478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.10.001>